

PROBONO

D8.15 PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY

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Contributors:

Partner	Contributor
SIN	Salima Ismayilzada

Peer reviewed by:

Partner	Reviewer
CGBC	Ivan Fratrić
IRTSX	Ahmed Amrani

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DEFINITIONS¹

A Green Building (GB) (new or retrofit) is a building that, in its design, construction and operation, reduces or eliminates negative impacts, and can create positive impacts, on the climate, social, and natural environment. GBs preserve precious natural resources and improve quality of life¹. Specifically, this means that GBs should be very energy efficient, use extensively the potential of locally available renewable energy, use sustainable materials, and aim for a low environmental impact over the entire life cycle. GBs offer their users and residents a healthy climate and a high quality of stay, they are resilient e.g., to environmental change and contribute to social inclusion.

Green Neighbourhoods aligned with the European Green Deal², is a set of buildings over a delimited area, at a scale that is smaller than a district, with potential synergies, in particular in the area of energy. A green neighbourhood is a neighbourhood that allows for environmentally friendly, sustainable patterns and behaviours to flourish e.g., bioclimatic architecture, renewable energy, soft and zero-emission mobility etc. Green neighbourhoods are the building blocks of Positive Energy Districts (PEDs)³ by implementing key elements of PED energy systems. For example, the exchange of energy between buildings increases the share of local self-supply with climate-neutral energy and system efficiency. They also provide the technical conditions to enable Citizen Energy Communities⁴ and Renewable Energy Communities⁵ to be implemented.

Green Buildings and Neighbourhoods (GBN) in PROBONO are GBs integrated at delimited area or district level with green energy and green mobility management and appropriate infrastructure supported by policies, investments and stakeholders' engagement and behaviours that ensures just transition that maximise the economic and social cobenefits¹ considering a district profile (population size, socio-economic structure, and geographical and climate characteristics). Delivered in the right way, GBN infrastructure is a key enabler of inclusive growth, can improve the accessibility of housing and amenities, reduce poverty and inequality, widen access to jobs and education, make communities more resilient to climate change, and promote public health and wellbeing.

DGNB certification serves as a quality stamp ensuring the state of the building for buyers. The Green Building Council Denmark⁶ has established the German certification DGNB meaning 'German Society for Sustainable Buildings'. The Danish version of DGNB was created to obtain a common definition of what sustainability is towards and making it measurable. A consortium of experts was established from all parts of the construction sector. DGNB had to be reshaped for the Danish standards, practice, traditions, and laws but is now available to certify any construction project. They chose DGNB as an innovation-forward and sustainable future guarantee. DGNB diversifies itself by focusing on sustainability and not just the environment. DGNB creates a standardised framework for the construction operations conditions and creates a common language which facilitates communication between professions and helps organize and prioritize the efforts in long and complicated development phases.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)⁷ is a tool used for the systematic quantitative assessment of each material used, energy flows and environmental impacts of products or processes. LCA assesses various aspects associated with development of a product and its potential impact throughout a product's life (i.e. cradle to grave) from raw material acquisition, processing, manufacturing, use and finally its disposal. In PROBONO, LCA represents the statement of a building's total energy, resource consumption and environmental impact in the manufacture, transport, and replacement of materials and for its operation over its expected life. Social life cycle assessment (S-LCA)⁸ is a method to assess the social and sociological aspects of products, their actual and potential positive as well as negative impacts along the life cycle. Life-cycle costing (LCC)⁹ considers all the costs incurred during the lifetime of the product, work, or service.

¹ These definitions are identified in the PROBONO GA no 101037075 and they may be further refined according to the results of the project.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of Action (annex I of the Grant Agreement)
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PO	Project Officer
PS	Project Secretariat
QM	Quality Management
SC	Scientific Coordinator
SM	Social Media
TL	Task Leader
ToC	Table of Contents
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Executive summary

Communication and dissemination activities play a vital role in creating awareness and common knowledge about the PROBONO project. This document presents an overview of the visual identity of the PROBONO project, together with the visual identity colours, typeface, logo, communication channels, and project website. These will help differentiate and recognize the project worldwide.

The most important element of the project's visual identity is the website which will be the main hub for all relevant news and information. The website is intended to be easy to navigate, and the main menu contains information "About" the project, as well as "Members", "Enablers", "Pilots", "Reports", and "Contact" sections for now. Furthermore, the PROBONO social media channels have been integrated into the website as part of the news feed on the homepage. This functionality will keep the website updated at all times.

Through a flexible and structured communication content plan, WP8 will ensure the overall quality of the website and social media content.

1 Introduction

1.1 Mapping PROBONO Outputs

The purpose of this section is to map PROBONO's GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project's respective outputs and work performed. D8.15 (Project Visual Identity) addresses Task 8.1 (Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities) which consists of ST8.1.1 (Dissemination Strategy & Communication Plan), ST8.1.2 (Dissemination & Communication material), and ST8.1.3 (Dissemination & Communication activities). Out of these three subtasks, D8.15 mainly handles the requirements of ST8.1.2 (Dissemination and Communication material). The primary purpose of ST8.1.2 is to establish a project promotion profile with a logo, to design templates and design marketing guideline for visualization, and to create a website and social media channels for the PROBONO project. In this respect, the logo of the project was designed and integrated into all communication and dissemination materials. Moreover, the graphical layout guideline of the project, together with templates, were created and approved by PST. Additionally, the website of the project was designed and launched under the URL www.probonoh2020.eu. Six social media platforms of the project (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube, and Wikipedia) were integrated into this website.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
Task 8.1. Dissemination Strategy, Communication Plan and Activities (M1-M60)	<p>ST8.1.2. Dissemination & Communication material.</p> <p>Create a project promotion profile with logo, design manual and templates for visualization. Project narratives will be identified as a part of knowledge analysis for user identification purposes. A design marketing guideline will be produced which will consist of standardized project logos, templates for PowerPoint and Word, and a banner for email signatures. In addition, posters, one pager, and flyers will be produced to be used at relevant events. Furthermore, the project website will be created and maintained from the beginning of the project and after its lifetime. It will present key outcomes in the form of news articles, reports, presentations etc. 5 professional videos highlighting the living labs, their challenges, the project vision, and expected outcomes will be produced. PROBONO will have accounts in several social media network communities, such as Twitter, Facebook,</p>	Chapter 2-4 and Annexes I-IV	Project Visual Identity is described along with the graphical layout, website, and communication channels of the project. Templates for External Deliverables, Internal Deliverables, Power Point Presentation and Meeting Minutes are also included in Annexes I - IV.

	<p>YouTube, and LinkedIn. All accounts will be integrated into the project website. The main objective will be to increase outreach by informing citizens at large, as well as different stakeholder groups, about PROBONO's purpose and its potential contribution to a more efficient, reliable, and sustainable buildings. The social networks will also be used to collect various feedback and extract information that will be utilised in dissemination and communication of the PROBONO project.</p>		
DELIVERABLE			
<p>D8.15: Project visual identity This report formulates the findings of T8.1 and explores the step of establishing the project's website and communication channels.</p>			

Table 1: Adherence to PROBONO's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

1.2 Purpose of the document

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide an evaluation of implemented activities and update the schedule for the dissemination and communications activities of the project. The report will be based on the D8.15 - Project Visual Identity, which contains establishing the project website and communication channels.

1.3 Scope of the document

This document will outline the completed dissemination and communication activities in the context of project visual identity up to M9.

1.4 Structure of the document

This document will first describe graphical layout guideline of the project together with created templates in Section 2. Section 3 will explain the structure of the project website that coordinated, established, and executed by SIN. This will be followed by Section 4 reporting in detail about the communication channels (social media accounts and newsletters) of the project. Finally, Section 5 will highlight the conclusions and the plans of action to be implemented in the next months.

2 Visual Identity of the Project

2.1 Logo

The thought behind the PROBONO logo (see Figure 1) is the merger between sustainability, technology, and the future of green cities. The colours of the logo are related to the sustainability aspect of the project, with two versions of the colour green. The supporting element to the typeface depicts a city landscape built up of nodes that supports the technical network running the city. We have selected an organic typeface to take “the edge” off the hard tech symbolism and focus on the inhabitants and end-users of the project. The logo also has a variation of two more colours: White and Black (See Figure 1):

Figure 1: PROBONO - Logo (left), logo in white (middle), alternative logo in black (right)

2.2 Typeface

The main graphic typeface of the project is *Dosis*. *Manrope* is preferred web font and body text. Moreover, *Calibri Light* is a work font for Word, Excel, PPT, etc (See Figure 4)

Figure 2: PROBONO - Typeface

2.3 Colours

The main colour of the PROBONO project visuals is Nordic Green (# 5f977a) while the secondary colour is Macha Green (# 90c09a). Alternate background colour is defined as White Peach (#f2f4d3). Amethyst (# 8F277D) would be used as the contrast colour and its black version would be Asphalt (# 303030). For more visual explanation, please see Figure 5 below.

Figure 3: PROBONO - Colours

2.4 Templates

Based on the graphical layout guideline of the project, several templates (see Annexes) have been created for different purposes, but mainly to unify the communication message and style and to ease the building of communication materials during the project:

- Deliverable (public/private)
- PowerPoint presentation template
- Minutes of Meeting (MoM) template

The templates have been sent to all PST members via email and will be available in the PROBONO Teams channel in the WP8 folder. Additional templates can be created if necessary.

3 Website

3.1 Overview

The PROBONO website is available with the URL www.probonoh2020.eu and will function as the main hub and a key tool for all relevant information and news about the project. The website will present the objectives, expected impacts and key outcomes of the project.

The website will host:

- Executive Summary of the project
- Presentation of project partners
- Presentation of Pilot sites
- Presentation of Enablers
- Dissemination of results and deliverables
- Links to Social Media pages
- Newsletter subscription

The website will be updated and improved in line with the progress of the project. In the time following the end of the project, the website is meant to work as a digital archive and showcase the project's goals, results, and impacts.

3.2 Structure

The website has been created on a WordPress platform by using customized SIN templates as the main theme. The official language of the website is English. The structure of the website is illustrated in Figure 6. The subsequent paragraphs will give more detailed information on each webpage. Moreover, additional pages can be added as the project progresses to reflect updates and milestones. Webpages can also be re-arranged to more adequately reflect the PROBONO brand and vision.

Figure 4: PROBONO Website Structure

3.2.1 Home Page

The primary purpose of the homepage is to create the first impression about the project and encourage engagement. The webpage will provide an overview of the project and easy access to News, Enablers, Pilots, SM accounts, etc.

Figure 5: Website Homepage

The homepage also consists of visuals that present vision and objectives of PROBONO (See Figure 8).

Figure 6: Website Homepage (2)

3.2.2 About

The drop-down menu, under the About button, consists of two main web pages: (1) About (general information about the project), and (2) Team (Managers and Advisory Board). In the “Team” webpage, members are presented with pictures, names, and contact information. These details enable the visitor to find and contact the relevant person easily for their request.

Figure 7: About Webpage

3.2.3 Members

“Members” webpage consists of a list of PROBONO project partners where visitors can find brief information on each partner. Moreover, the webpage will direct visitors to the main websites of the partners.

3.2.4 Enablers

The “Enablers” webpage provides brief information about each GBN Transition Acceleration Enabler of the PROBONO project. Since the target audience of the website is both experts and citizens, the webpage presents more user-friendly content on the enablers. Furthermore, a subpage for each Enabler will be added when there is progress within the project.

Figure 8: Enablers Webpage

3.2.5 Pilots

The “Pilots” webpage presents six Living Labs of the project where visitors will be able to find brief information about each Pilot. They will need to click the "Read More" button in order to get more detailed information about the Pilots, which will then direct them to a new webpage.

Figure 9: Pilots Webpage

3.2.6 News

This section will present the news and events on two separate pages. This page is intended to provide the visitor with all the latest (public) news and updates from the project. The page is hidden on the website now and will appear when there will be news on the project.

3.2.7 Reports

This page presents Public Deliverables of the PROBONO project. Each Deliverable will have PR-worthy title. Moreover, the keyword will be defined for each deliverable for maximizing search engine optimization of the website. Visitors will be able to download the deliverable files in PDF format.

Figure 10: Reports Webpage

3.2.8 Contact

This page is meant to enable website visitors to contact the project manager. They can send their inquiries by fulfilling required details such as name, surname, etc. The PROBONO project will use these details both to answer the question adequately and for communication/dissemination activities.

The image shows a contact form on a website. At the top, there is a dark blue header with the word "Contact" in white, followed by the text "If you would like to get in touch, contact us here". To the right of the text is a faint white line-art illustration of a building and a tree. Below the header is a white form area. The form contains several input fields: "First Name", "Last Name", "Email *", "Company", "Phone", and "Job Title". There is also a larger "Additional information" field. At the bottom of the form is a blue "Submit" button.

Figure 11: Contact Webpage

4 Communication Channels

4.1 Social Media Channels

One of the most efficient ways to reach larger audiences is to actively use digital tools. These digital tools enable us to disseminate information through the project collaboration platform, the website, and social SM channels. The PROBONO project will be visible and active on six social media platforms: Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, YouTube, and Wikipedia. These channels will provide followers with all important updates from the project, to create awareness about the project and engage stakeholders. The profiles are integrated into the website, allowing website visitors to see real-time updates.

To ensure that all vital information and newsworthy activities/results are communicated to relevant audiences, a strategic plan will be established. WP8 leader, together with the Communication Committee, will implement this plan on social media.

- The PROBONO **Twitter** account has been created with the URL <https://twitter.com/probonoh2020>. It will be used to cover ongoing news and updates

from the consortium partners, and for collecting input and information. Twitter will enable the stakeholders to be involved directly with live discussions during a workshop or event.

- PROBONO **Facebook** page, has been created with the URL <https://www.facebook.com/ProbonoH2020>. Unlike Twitter, Facebook allows longer texts and its news feed algorithm favours video content and images.
- PROBONO **Instagram** account, has been created with the URL <https://www.instagram.com/probono2020/> (username: @probono2020). Instagram photos and videos. Instagram will be used to provide an interactive and visual presentation of the project activities to stand out from other information and advertisement in the news feed.
- The **LinkedIn** page created for the project has the URL: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/probonoh2020/>. The LinkedIn account of the project will target businesses and stakeholders and will be used as the main social media channel to communicate and disseminate events, posters, and updates.

Figure 12: LinkedIn Account

- PROBONO also has a **YouTube** channel, with the URL: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCSrwUTS0Xx1wHH0MgJMTEL>. This account will be used as a main hub for all videos created in the project.
- The PROBONO will also have a **Wikipedia** page as a dissemination tool for the project. Although the page is ready to be published, it cannot be public before academic publications on PROBONO.

4.2 Newsletters

Two kinds of newsletters for the PROBONO project are planned to be released - External and Internal. Both of them will be used to inform and engage the stakeholders about the project's progress, activities, results, and outcomes. However, Internal Newsletter will be used as an internal communication tool for PST members. The same design (see Figure 15) will be used for both newsletters. The design is created based on the graphical layout guideline of the project.

Figure 13: PROBONO - Newsletter

Conclusion

This document presents the Visual Identity of the PROBONO project by describing the graphical layout, website, and communication channels of the project. It outlines the colour palette, typeface and templates of the project, the structure of the website, and communication channels (social media channels and newsletter) utilized to reach the proper target audiences and goals and the measures to be undertaken to maximize the impact and awareness creation of the project.

“PROBONO will show how a people-centred, green and sustainable approach to renovation, however small, can stimulate sustainable neighbourhoods and the well-being of communities”. Therefore, it is significant to promote PROBONO and its results to a multitude of audiences and engaging them in a two-way exchange. All of these communication and dissemination activities will help a successful promotion of "creating and enabling a lasting, committed community of practice to strengthen and foster the uptake of positive energy buildings, low carbon, high air quality and the conservation and restoration of ecosystems and biodiversity"¹⁰ (PROBONO Project, 2021).

ANNEXES

Annex I

External Deliverable Template

Annex II

Internal Deliverable Template

Deliverable n°:	Dx.y
Deliverable name:	Name
Version:	1.0
Release date:	dd/02/2022
Dissemination level:	xxxx (Public, Confidential)
Status:	xxxx (Draft, Peer-reviewed, Submitted, Approved)
Author:	SIN – Salima Ismayilzada

It is necessary to include background for the work reported in the deliverable, reasons for choosing a solution, discussion among possible solutions before choosing one, relation to other project deliverables, tasks, and WPs (inputs used, outputs created), as well as concrete conclusions of the documents.

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Annex III

Meeting Minutes Template

Meeting:	TCC meeting, M2
Date:	dd/mm/2022
Location:	
Version:	1.0
Release date:	dd/02/2022
Dissemination Level:	Internal
Author:	SIN – Salima Ismayilzada

Minutes

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Annex IV

Power Point Presentation Template

References

¹ <https://www.worldgbc.org/what-green-building>

² European_Green_Deal_EN_200710_fin

³ SET-Plan Action 3.2:

https://setis.ec.europa.eu/system/files/setplan_smartcities_implementationplan.pdf

⁴ Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 5 Renewable Energy Directive (EU)

⁵ Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20012018/2001

⁶ <https://dk-gbc.dk/publikation/guide-to-dgnb-for-buildings>

⁷ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/16cd2d1d-2216-11e8-ac73-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

⁸ <https://www.lifecycleinitiative.org/starting-life-cycle-thinking/life-cycle-approaches/social-lca/>

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/lcc.htm>

¹⁰ PROBONO Project. (2021). PROPOSAL_101037075-PROBONO-H2020-LC-GD-2020-7-PART_B_Section_1.